

INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

Scopus || Electronic journal specializing in Scopus

ISSUE 12

Acceptance of papers **December, 2025**

Acceptance of papers

Published monthly

Topics

economics, technology, social sciences

ISSN 3060-5229

Digital Object Identifier

Visit the website t.me/scopus_IST2100

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THE SCIENTIFIC-POPULAR ELECTRONIC JOURNAL **"INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY"** HAS BEEN REGISTERED UNDER THE NUMBER **C-5669633** BY THE AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND MASS COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA) OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN, EFFECTIVE FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

CONTACTS

Phone: **+998 50 737 87 88**

Website: <https://ist-journal.uz>

Email: innovationist2025@gmail.com

The scientific electronic journal "Innovation Science and Technology" has been included in the list of scientific publications recommended for the publication of main scientific results of dissertations for the award of PhD and DSc degrees in economics and technical sciences, in accordance with the Resolution No. 370 of the Presidium of the Higher Attestation Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated May 8, 2025.

Electronic publication, Issue 12. 341 pages.
Approved for publication on December, 2025.

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TYPES AND MEANS OF ADVERTISING IN THE FIELD OF TOURISM

Bahriyeva Zarina Nasimovna

Researcher at the Silk Road International
University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage

[ORCID: 0009-0003-7025-5236](https://orcid.org/0009-0003-7025-5236)

Abstract: The article analyzes the types and means of advertising used in the field of tourism, reveals the role and importance of advertising in promoting a tourist product on the market, studies its influence on the decision-making process of tourists, and pays special attention to traditional and digital types of advertising, including advertising media, internet platforms, social networks, and mobile technologies.

Key words: tourism sector, hotel services, classification of advertising, consumers of tourist services, informative advertising, persuasive advertising.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada turizm sohasida qo'llaniladigan reklama turlari va vositalari tahlil qilingan bo'lib, turistik mahsulotni bozorda ilgari surishda reklamaning o'рни va ahamiyati ochib berilgan, uning turistlar qaror qabul qilish jarayoniga ta'siri o'rganilgan hamda tadqiqotda an'anaviy va raqamli reklama turlari, jumladan ommaviy axborot vositalari, internet platformalar, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar va mobil texnologiyalar orqali amalga oshiriladigan reklama vositalariga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: turizm sohasi, mehmonxona xizmati, reklama klassifikatsiyasi, turistik xizmat iste'molchilari, ma'lumot beruvchi reklama, ishoniruvchi reklama.

Аннотация: В статье анализируются виды и средства рекламы, используемые в сфере туризма, раскрывается роль и значение рекламы в продвижении туристического продукта на рынке, изучается ее влияние на процесс принятия решений туристами, а в исследовании особое внимание уделяется традиционным и цифровым видам рекламы, в том числе средствам массовой информации, интернет-платформам, социальным сетям и мобильным технологиям.

Ключевые слова: Сфера туризма, гостиничные услуги, классификация рекламы, потребители туристических услуг, информационная реклама, убедительная реклама.

INTRODUCTION

The tourism sector is one of the fastest-growing sectors of the global economy. So why is advertising so important for this network? Since a tourist product (travel, tour, hotel service) is not material, but emotional and rich in experience, the consumer encounters information asymmetry in the decision-making process. In such conditions, effective management of advertising activities determines the competitive advantage of tourism entities.

The global tourism market showed real growth of 11% by the end of 2024 (UNWTO, 2025). In the post-pandemic environment, competition is determined not by the quality of service, but by the speed and accuracy of information about the service. Due to the fact that the tourism product has the property of "invisible" and delayed consumption, the management of advertising activities has risen to a strategic level.

Modern tourism cannot be imagined without advertising, because it is the most effective means of the tourist enterprise's efforts to convey information to its customers, change their behavior, attract attention to the services offered, demonstrate their social significance, and create a positive image of the enterprise itself. "Effective advertising is the most important tool for achieving the goals of marketing strategy in general and communication strategy in particular. In a certain period, experts noticed that advertising, which is a product of urban culture and has a serious socio-regulatory potential, has become one of the important mechanisms influencing various processes in society, performing socio-pedagogical and socio-cultural tasks. Gradually, advertising began to shape the values and standards of society, the norms and rules of the individual and the

group, public ideas about the ideal model of life and consumption, therefore it became important to analyze its influence, subject matter, and essence.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

According to I. Vikentyev and Durovich, advertising in tourism is classified according to a number of characteristics. Depending on the advertising object, we can talk about two main types of advertising - product and image advertising.

The main task of product advertising is to form and stimulate demand for tourist products. Such advertising "informs potential buyers about its services, generates interest, and stimulates sales." "And prestigious or image advertising is advertising the services of this enterprise, which distinguishes it well from competitors. The goal of such advertising is to create an attractive image in the public and, first of all, among active and potential buyers, which will inspire confidence in the tourist company itself and in all the services it offers."

A.P. Durovich distinguishes types of advertising in tourism based on their characteristics. "He believes that in practice, in its original form, there are very few prestigious and product advertisements. As a rule, they are carried out together, only in the first case attention is paid to the company's image, in the second - to the products it offers. For example, in terms of direction, it distinguishes between advertising the capabilities of a tourist enterprise and advertising its needs."

In the tourism industry, there are various ways to develop the tourism market. "Using a trademark or regional cooperation method to attract consumer attention yields good results." However, "the use of advertising as the main means of success requires a thorough analysis of scientific, social, and economic means of behavior."

«Effective means of promoting tourism include books (city or region) throughout the country, advertising, CDs, websites, email, radio, posters, television, press, direct mail, databases, tourist information centers and exhibitions.» According to W.R. Dos, «advertising can be used to promote domestic tourism through radio and television, in addition, travel brochures and posters provide valuable information about the city visited by the tourist and its maps, and are also a widely used and effective means of promoting this industry, informing the consumer about newly opened travel agencies.»

«Enterprises in the tourism sector conduct research on the needs of potential consumers, as well as promote their tourism products in the market and strive to create the most optimal advertising for perception.» Of course, advertising increases the demand for goods. Moreover, «advertising can influence the formation of needs, that is, it in some way determines lifestyle; through advertising, people become acquainted with the latest news, achievements of modern technologies, which determines the corresponding level of needs.»

The results of research conducted by Professors A.G.Awan, M.Ismail, C.P.Majeed, and F.Ghazal show that advertising has a great influence on consumer behavior. «Factors such as need, pleasure, preference, product memorization and promotion greatly help to shape and change consumer purchasing demand, which is a very positive sign for advertising and marketing companies. Their results also confirmed the research model, which shows that advertising has a significant impact on consumer purchasing demand and expands their choice. This research will be useful for marketing and advertising companies in promoting their products.»

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology of this study is based on the collection of secondary and primary data obtained from scientific publications, international tourism statistics, and analytical reports. In addition, qualitative content analysis of advertising materials and comparative analysis of traditional and digital advertising tools were applied. The collected data were processed using descriptive analysis and logical generalization to identify key trends and patterns.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In the promotion of a tourist product, there is a variety of types of advertising, which can be grouped according to various characteristics.

According to the advertising object, advertising is divided into the following three main categories: product advertising, image (prestige) advertising, and tourist destination advertising.

The task of product advertising is to create and stimulate demand for a tourist product.

Image advertising is aimed at forming a positive image of the tourist enterprise among the public, in particular, among active and potential clients, which ensures that this image creates confidence in both the enterprise itself and all its tourist services.

In practice, product and image advertisements are usually used together, not separately. The difference is that in some cases, the main focus is on the company's brand, while in other cases, its tourist offers are given restraint.

Advertising of tourist destinations (Latin *destinazia* - «location») is aimed at creating an attractive image of the country or its specific territory, thereby increasing the flow of tourists. According to international experience, the more well-known a region is in terms of tourism, the easier and cheaper it is to bring the products offered by tour operators to the market. In most cases, destination advertising is carried out at the expense of budget funds; in the foreign market, this function is performed by national tourism organizations (associations) and their representative offices abroad.

According to the method of advertising implementation, it can be divided into direct and hidden forms.

In direct advertising the advertiser is explicitly indicated and directly promotes a specific tourism product or business.

Hidden advertising is carried out in a disguised manner without the use of any open advertising channels, and neither the advertiser nor the nature of the advertisement is directly determined (Table 1).

Table 1. Classification of advertising by the level of territorial coverage

Degree	Definition	Scientific and practical significance	Benefits	Restrictions
Local	Advertising campaigns aimed at a retail outlet or individual settlement.	Uses micro-regional segmentation (in the STP model <i>Segment-Target-Position</i>), taking into account local needs and mental characteristics.	Relatively low costs, quick feedback, personalized message.	The coverage is narrow, scaling is difficult.
Regional	It covers a specific economic-geographical region.	Integrated approach to <i>regional economic factors</i> in PEST analysis.	Brand awareness, cooperation effect (clustering).	High logistics and media print costs for advertising coordination.
Nationwide	Unified image campaign on a national scale.	The concept of Nation Branding (Anholt, 2002) and the basis of WTTC methodology.	The same corporate image, the same identity.	Requires custom content; target audience is heterogeneous.
International	Conducted in several countries or interregional areas.	UNWTO relies on the theory of cross-cultural communication, harmonized with the rules of the «Global Code of Ethics for Tourism.»	Export orientation, currency attraction, synergy with ODA assistance programs.	Legal differences, cultural barriers, large budgets.

For example, a newspaper announcement about a new type of product is considered direct advertising. However, if the same newspaper analyzes the upcoming season and publishes an article showing this particular product as the most profitable offer, this is considered hidden advertising. Practice shows that covert advertising often yields significant results. Therefore, product placement (Eng. product placement) is rapidly developing in marketing - it creates the possibility of skillfully connecting advertising content with tourism products in feature films, literary works, or television programs (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Ad types by functional direction

Throughout the life cycle of a tourist product, advertising appeals are usually divided into three directions: informative, convincing, and reminding advertising.

- The task of informative advertising is to inform potential clients about the enterprise and its types of products, their features, advantages, and innovations. This type of advertising, as a rule, is of great importance at the stage when the product enters the market for the first time and it is necessary to form initial demand.
- Suggestive advertising is a relatively aggressive technique and is triggered when sales are growing rapidly. Its goal is to convince the consumer that this particular tourist product is superior to competitors, to increase the desire to buy, and to stimulate sales through sales supporting factors.
- Reminder advertising serves to maintain a constantly updated perception of the product (or enterprise) that has found its place in the market. Usually, this type of advertising is preferred when the product reaches maturity or «ripeness.»

In marketing theory, advertising is a central element of the communication process between market participants. Advertising for tourist products manifests itself not only as a mechanism for the formation of demand, but also as a sectoral mechanism for strengthening the brand of the country or region, diversifying tourism infrastructure, and positively influencing macroeconomic indicators (currency receipts, employment, etc.). Therefore, it is advisable to systematically study the advertising strategy of a tourist enterprise in two dimensions - territorial coverage and functional orientation (Table 2).

Table 2. Types of advertising by targeted impact

Type	The main point of view in any ad	Features	Typical example
Rational advertising	Addresses the consumer's conscious decision-making process	- Clearly and measurably shows benefits and advantages (discount, bonus, guarantee). - In most cases, logical argumentation, statistical evidence, price-quality ratio are included in the text. - Impact model: AIDA Logical basis at the «Desire» stage in (Attention → Interest → Desire → Action).	A commercial offer, such as «Book early - 25% discount, free accommodation for children.»

Emotional advertising	Stimulates consumer motivation through emotions and subconscious	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Uses visual (pictures, videos) and audio symbols, metaphors, aesthetic imagery. - Illuminates psychologically valuable attributes (image, status, romance, sense of security). - Impact model: <i>E-A-U</i> (Emotion → Association → Unification) - evokes a positive memory or association with the product. 	Video of a trip to Greece: views of the sea and rivers, attractive tourists warming in the sun, antique monuments in the background.
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Systematic study of advertising activities for tourism enterprises in terms of territorial coverage and functional orientation creates an important methodological basis for making strategic decisions. The combination of scientific views (nation branding, STP, PEST, CSR) and practical tools (digital analytics, programmatic media, supply-chain management) forms priority competitive advantages and serves to occupy a stable position in the market.

Current advertising is often in the form of a hybrid of rational and emotional elements in different proportions, and it is considered effective to be mixed depending on socio-demographic, cultural context, and product position.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Research shows that while traditional advertising is still effective today, advertising carried out through modern digital platforms and social networks significantly increases its effectiveness in attracting tourists. As a result of scientific analysis, it was established that the integrated use of types of advertising, the correct implementation of audience segmentation, and attention to the quality of content are priority factors in tourism marketing. On this basis, tourism entities should create advertising strategies by combining digital and traditional tools, which will serve to increase the competitiveness of tourism products and services.

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Proofreader: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Layout and Designer: Oloviddin Sobir ugli

2025. № 12

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